

Spectroscopic characterization of some copper(II) complexes

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Abstract : 1-(Phenylazo)-2-naphthol (PANH) has three potential donor sites and thus it acts as a very good chelating agent. This ligand has been used for complexation with Cu^{II} ions to synthesize the complexes of general formula Cu(PAN)₂L_n, where L = secondary ligands like pyridine, picoline, H₂O and n = 0, 1 and 2. These complexes have been characterized by their elemental analysis, conductivity measurement, magnetic moment at room temperature, infrared spectra and electronic spectra. The ligand PANH is found to have coordinated through deprotonated phenolic oxygen and azonitrogen forming a six membered chelate with two conjugate π -bonds in chelate ring. The magnetic moment values reveal the mononuclear nature of complexes while their electronic spectra reveal the geometry of the complexes. Cu(PAN)₂ complex is found square planar while Cu(PAN)₂L and Cu(PAN)₂L₂ are found square pyramidal and tetragonally distorted octahedral respectively.

Keywords : Square pyramidal, teragonally distorted octahedral.

Introduction

Growing interest has been directed toward copper-sulphur chemistry in the past decade¹⁻⁵. This is related to the natural occurrence of copper-thiolate and copper-thioether bonds encountered in a wide variety of proteins⁶ and particularly in redox active proteins with electron transfer functions. Recently special focus has been given on complexes of Cu^{II} with nitrogen donors, as the catalytic amidation of aryl halides has become an important synthetic process for which the oldest examples were reported with copper catalysts⁷. Much effort has been spent recently by many groups to improve upon the original copper catalysts for the coupling of aryl halides with nitrogen nucleophiles by conducting the reaction with nitrogen ligands⁸. The ligands used for this chemistry have included bipyridines and phenanthrolines⁹⁻¹², 1,2-diamines^{13,14}, α -amino acids¹⁵, bis-pyridylimines¹⁶ etc. Complexes of silylaldehyde, benzoyl and 2-picoloxy hydrazones with transition metals have also been reported¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Late transition-metal amido complexes have been proposed as important intermediate in many catalytic and organic reactions because of their relatively labile M-N bonds²⁰⁻²². The complexes of *o*-hydroxy oximes have received appreciable attention due to their structural feature of general interest²³⁻²⁸. The study of these oximes

of Cu^{II} is also important in view of their possible application as biochemical models^{29,30}, and as semiconducting model^{31,32}. In this paper, we report the synthesis and characterization of some Cu^{II} complexes with 1-(phenylazo)-2-naphthol having nitrogen and oxygen as potential donor sites as main ligand and pyridine, α -picoline as secondary ligands.

Results and discussion

The microanalytical data have been given in Table 1, on the basis of which the complexes were formulated as [Cu(PAN)₂L_n] where PAN = 1-(phenylazo)-2-naphthol and L = pyridine, α -picoline, H₂O and n = 0, 1 and 2. The conductivity values of complexes in DMSO solution of 10⁻³ M concentration fall in the range of 15-25 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹ which are indicative of non electrolytic nature of complexes^{33,34}.

Infrared spectra : Out of the cumbersome IR spectra of the ligand and complexes some important bands and their assignments have been given in Table 2.

The broad band at 3200 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the free ligand is assigned to the H-bonded phenolic -OH group³⁵. In all the complexes this band disappears showing the coordination through deprotonated phenolic oxy-

Table 1. Microanalytical data

Sl. no.	Compds.	Color	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)				Λ_m DMSO slution ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
				M	C	H	N	
1.	Ligand (PANH)	Brown	115	-	74.42 (74.81)	4.11 (4.00)	11.29 (11.10)	-
2.	Cu(PAN) ₂	Green	270	11.35 (11.18)	68.63 (68.82)	4.29 (4.10)	10.00 (9.91)	18
3.	Cu(PAN) ₂ Py	Light green	265	9.95 (9.81)	69.54 (69.80)	4.54 (4.41)	10.96 (10.78)	20
4.	Cu(PAN) ₂ (Py) ₂	Dull green	269	9.20 (9.06)	73.00 (73.31)	4.92 (4.78)	12.16 (12.00)	25
5.	Cu(PAN) ₂ (α -Pico)	Light green	271	9.73 (9.61)	69.88 (69.97)	4.75 (4.61)	10.72 (10.59)	22
6.	Cu(PAN) ₂ (α -Pico) ₂	Green	278	8.49 (8.37)	70.63 (70.86)	5.08 (4.91)	11.23 (11.00)	15
7.	Cu(PAN) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	Green	259	10.66 (10.47)	64.48 (64.69)	4.70 (4.49)	9.40 (9.31)	24

Table 2. Important IR bands (cm^{-1})

Bands in free ligand	Cu (PAN) ₂	Cu (PAN) ₂ Py	Cu (PAN) ₂ (Py) ₂	Cu (PAN) ₂ (α -Pico)	Cu(PAN) ₂ (α -Pico) ₂	Cu (PAN) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	Assignment
-	-	-	-	-	-	3400	ν_{OH} of coordinated H ₂ O
3200(br)	-	-	-	-	-	-	H-bonded $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$
3300(w)	3010	3015	3010	3010	3020	3075	$\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ of aromatic ring
1610(m)	1630	1630	1635	1525	1530	1535	Aromatic ring
1580(s)	1575	1580	1585	1580	1580	1580	Conjugation of benzene ring with azo group
1525(s)	1530	1535	1535	1525	1530	1535	Aromatic ring
1480(w)	1480	1480	1480	1480	1480	1480	Aromatic ring
1455(w)	1450	1455	1455	1455	1455	1455	Aromatic ring
1410(vw)	1380	1295	1300	1310	1295	1295	$\nu_{\text{N=N}}$
1290(s)	-	-	-	-	-	-	$\nu_{\text{Ar-C-N}}$
1040(m)	1050	1055	1055	1050	1055	1055	$\nu_{\text{Ar-C-O}}$
-	-	-	-	-	-	900	$\nu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$
-	-	-	-	765	765	-	α -Pico
-	-	760	760	-	-	-	$\nu_{\text{Py ring}}$
-	490	495	510	495	500	490	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$
-	420	410	420	420	420	415	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$

gen. This mode of coordination of the ligand may further be substantiated by an increase in the $\nu_{\text{Ar-C-O}}$ stretching frequency (1040 cm^{-1} in free ligand) by 10 to 15 cm^{-1} in the complexes. The weak band at 3000 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ stretching in the plane of the aromatic ring. The appearance of four bands in between 1455 to 1610 cm^{-1} can be reasonably assigned to aromatic ring

vibration³⁶⁻³⁸. The bands at 1610 cm^{-1} and 1525 cm^{-1} taken in conjugation with $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ stretching band at 3000 cm^{-1} afford a ready means of recognition of aromatic ring in the ligand. A sharp band at 1580 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of the free ligand shows the conjugation of benzene ring with azogroup³⁹. The very weak band at 1410 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the free ligand is well assigned to

$\nu_{N=N}$ group³⁵ which suffers red shift by 30–35 cm^{-1} in all the complexes which is indicative of the involvement of azonitrogen in coordination to Cu^{II} ion. This may further be substantiated by an increase in $\nu_{\text{Ar-C-N}}$ vibration occurring at 1290 cm^{-1} in free ligand by about 10 cm^{-1} in the spectra of complexes. The coordination through deprotonated phenolic oxygen and azo nitrogen of the ligand is further confirmed by the appearance of the new bands at 490–510 cm^{-1} and 410–420 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{M=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ respectively in the spectra of the complexes^{40–43}.

The coordination sites of the ligand 1-(phenylazo)-2-naphthol is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The appearance of new bands at 760 cm^{-1} in complexes **3** and **4** and at 765 cm^{-1} in complexes **5** and **6** shows the presence of pyridine and α -picoline in the coordination sphere of complexes **3–6** respectively^{44–46}. The appearance of the new band at 3400 cm^{-1} in complex **7** due to $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ stretching of coordinated water and another at 900 cm^{-1} due to rocking mode of vibration of coordinated water confirms the presence of H_2O in the coordination sphere of this complex.

Electronic spectra and magnetic moment :

The complex $\text{Cu}(\text{PAN})_2$ displays three bands, i.e. at 12100, 16900 and 18800 cm^{-1} in electronic spectra. Just as it is convenient to introduce the quantity D_q ($D_q = 5 \mu r^4/6a^6$) to parameterize the cubic symmetry crystal field energies, an equivalent quantity C_p is defined for the lower symmetry components⁴⁷ where $C_p = (2/7)Zer^2/a^3$ and for square planar complexes $C_p > 3D_q$. For square planar symmetry d_{z^2} is not always lower in energy than d_{xz} , d_{yz} . The energy levels of the different components of 2D term of a d^9 system in square planar crystal field may be given as⁴⁷: ${}^2A_{1g} (2C_p - 18/7 D_q) > {}^2E_g (C_p + 12/7 D_q) > {}^2B_{2g} (-2C_p + 32/7 D_q) > {}^2B_{1g} (-2C_p - 38/7 D_q)$ or ${}^2E_g >$

$A_{1g} > {}^2B_{2g} > {}^2B_{1g}$. Generally, $C_p/D_q > 4$ for the first sequence. If the above mentioned three transitions are assigned to the following transitions in accordance with the first energy sequence as below :

$$\nu_1 = {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g} = 12100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

corresponds to $10D_q$

$$\nu_2 = {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g = 16900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

corresponds to $3C_p + 50/7D_q$

$$\nu_3 = {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g} = 18800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

corresponds to $4C_p + 20/7D_q$

the value of $D_q = 1210 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. If C_p is calculated from ν_3 it comes to be 3635 cm^{-1} . From this value of C_p , ν_2 is calculated from $3C_p + 50/7D_q$ and is found to be 19562 cm^{-1} which is greater than ν_3 (18800 cm^{-1}). Obviously the above assignment of electronic bands is not quite good. So the assignment of these bands is made here according to the second sequence as below :

$$\nu_1 = {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}, \nu_2 = {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g} \text{ and}$$

$$\nu_3 = {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$$

From this assignment the value of C_p calculated from ν_3 is found 3381 cm^{-1} and from this value of C_p , the calculated value of ν_2 comes to be 16981 cm^{-1} which is very close to 16900 cm^{-1} the experimental value. The $C_p/D_q = 2.8$ is less than 4 which is indicative of the lower energy of ${}^2A_{1g}$ than 2E_g . These bands and other parameters are well within the range of square planar complexes of Cu^{II} ⁴⁸. Its magnetic moment value at room temperature is 1.9 BM. From which nothing about square planar geometry could be inferred but it is in good agreement with the reported value for mono nuclear square planar complexes of Cu^{II} ion³³. The ν_1 is the measure of $10D_q$ and hence the $10D_q$ value of this 4-coordinate square planar complex of Cu^{II} is 12100 cm^{-1} . Had this 4-coordinate complex been tetrahedral there would have been a band near infrared⁴⁹. Thus the possibility of tetrahedral geometry of this complex is ruled out.

The μ_{eff} values of complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{PAN})_2\text{Py}]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{PAN})_2 \alpha\text{-Pic}]$ are 1.80 and 1.83 BM which show the presence of one unpaired electron. This also confirms the monomeric nature of the complexes. In electronic spectra they display three bands i.e. (i) 11500 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 3.1$) and 11600 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 2.9$), (ii) 14000 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 5.2$)

and 14100 cm⁻¹ (ε = 5.0) and (iii) 14800 cm⁻¹ (ε = 9.0) and 15000 cm⁻¹ (ε = 9.1). They are 5-coordinate complexes and may have either trigonal bipyramidal or square pyramidal geometry. Generally for a trigonal bipyramidal 5-coordinate complex, three bands appear between 10500–14600 cm⁻¹ while a square pyramidal complex displays three bands between 11400 to 15000 cm⁻¹. Secondly if the complex is trigonal bipyramidal, there is greater absorption to lower energy band while for a square pyramidal Cu^{II} complex the greater absorption occurs with high energy band⁴⁹. On this basis the above mentioned three bands are assigned to the following transition in square pyramidal field^{50–52}.

$$v_1 = {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g} = 11500 \text{ and } 11600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

$$v_2 = {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g} = 14000 \text{ and } 14100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

$$v_3 = {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g = 14800 \text{ and } 15500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

The μ_{eff} values of complexes **4**, **6** and **7** are 1.9, 2.01 and 2.00 BM respectively which are well in agreement with one unpaired electron. In the electronic spectra of these complexes, three bands are displayed. Actually, ²T_{2g} and ²E_g components of ²D term of d⁹ system (Cu^{II}) undergo further splitting into ²E_g and ²B_{2g} and ²A_{1g} and ²B_{1g} respectively under tetragonal distortion. The energy associated with these levels may be given as below^{53,54}.

$${}^2B_{1g} = -6D_q - 2D_s + D_t \quad (i)$$

$${}^2A_{1g} = -6D_q + 2D_s + 6D_t \quad (ii)$$

$${}^2B_{2g} = 4D_q - 2D_s + D_t \quad (iii)$$

$${}^2E_g = 4D_q + D_s - 4D_t \quad (iv)$$

So, the expected three transitions correspond to the following energy changes.

$$v_1 = {}^2A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g} = 4D_s + 5D_t \quad (v)$$

$$v_2 = {}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g} = 10D_{q(xy)} \quad (vi)$$

$$v_3 = {}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g} = 10D_q + 3D_s - 5D_t \quad (vii)$$

$$v_1 + v_3 = 10D_q + 7D_s \quad (viii)$$

and D_t is given by expression

$$D_t = 4/7(D_{q(xy)} - D_{q(z)}) \quad (ix)$$

where D_{q(xy)} and D_{q(z)} represent the planar and the axial crystal field strength respectively.

The bands position and their assignment may be given in Table 3.

Table 3

Complexes	v ₁	v ₂	v ₃
Cu(PAN) ₂ (Py) ₂	12000	14000	17000
Cu(PAN) ₂ (α-Pico) ₂	9000	11200	13200
Cu(PAN) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	13400	15500	18100
Assignment	² B _{1g} → ² A _{1g}	² B _{1g} → ² B _{2g}	² B _{1g} → ² E _{cg}

v₁ is the measure of tetragonality in O_h complexes as it defines the tetragonal splitting of ²E_g level. In general the greater is the tetragonality, the longer is the axial bond length, the greater is the value of v₁. On the basis of tetragonality v₁, the order of tetragonal distortion power of axial ligands in present case may be given as H₂O > Py > α-picoline. α-Picoline due to +I effect and hyperconjugation effect of -CH₃ group at α-carbon, may have greater electron density on endocyclic N than pyridine and thus its greater coordination power forces it to be much closer to Cu^{II} along Z-axis and hence there is least distortion. This trend is further confirmed by their 10D_{q(xy)} values and blue shifting of their v₃ values. As the axial bond weakens, Cu^{II} becomes more electropositive and hence it attracts the in-plane ligands more strongly causing an increase in 10D_{q(xy)} values. As the axial field is weakened d_{xz} and d_{yz} become more and more stable causing greater gap between ²B_{1g} and ²E_g and hence v₃ suffers blue shift. On the basis of eqs. (v) to (ix), the values of the various crystal field parameters were calculated and given in the Table 4.

Table 4. (in cm⁻¹)

Complexes	10D _{q(xy)}	10D _{qz}	D _s	D _t
Cu(PAN) ₂ (Py) ₂	14200	1790	2114	709
Cu(PAN) ₂ (α-Pico) ₂	11200	1400	1600	560
Cu(PAN) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	15500	590	2285	852

These bands and the other crystal field parameters are indicative of distorted octahedral symmetry around Cu^{II} in these complexes^{53,54}.

Experimental

The alcoholic solutions of 0.01 mole (1.425 g) of benzene diazonium chloride and 0.01 mole (1.44 g) of 2-naphthol were taken together and heated for about one hour on water bath with stirring. On cooling the solution a brown precipitate appeared which was filtered and washed with alcohol and finally dried in an electric oven at 90 °C. The yield was found about 2 g (80%). Now the

alcoholic solutions of 0.01 mole (2.425 g) of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.02 mole (nearly 5 g) of 1-(phenylazo)-2-naphthol were mixed together and the resulting solution was refluxed for about four hours whereby a green precipitate appeared which was left for two hours to settle down. It was finally filtered and was washed with water and then with alcohol and then dried on anhydrous CaCl_2 in a desiccator. The yield was nearly 70%. Now this compound was treated with 0.01 mole and 0.02 mole of pyridine, α -picoline separately to get the pyridine, dipyridine, α -picoline, di- α -picoline adducts. The complexes were microanalysed for carbon, nitrogen and hydrogen. Copper was estimated iodometrically in all the complexes. The molar conductivity of complexes were measured on Elico conductivity bridge (Type CM82T) using 10^{-3} M DMSO solution. The magnetic moment of complexes were determined by Gouy balance at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ ($X_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ CGS units) as the calibrating agent. The IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer in nujol while electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer in DMSO solution of complexes.

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